

Gerlanugin, a new coumarin from *Gerbera lanuginosa*

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Phytochemical investigation on *Gerbera lanuginosa* Benth. afforded a new coumarin compound, gerlanugin [5-(1'-keto-2',3'-dimethylpropan-2',3'-epoxy)-7-methoxycoumarin] (1). Elucidation of its structure from spectral data are discussed.

The genus *Gerbera* is reported to possess a wide array of compounds, some of which exhibit antibacterial and medicinal properties¹. Previous phytochemical investigations on *G. lanuginosa* Benth. has elaborated a few coumarins. As a part of our research programme on plants possessing biological activity, we have investigated the whole plant of *G. lanuginosa*. In this communication we report the isolation and structure elucidation of a new coumarin designated as gerlanugin (1).

Results and discussion

Gerlanugin crystallized from hexane-chloroform as colourless needles, analysed for C₁₅H₁₄O₅ ([M]⁺ at *m/z* 274), m.p. 76–78°C. The colour reactions (positive coumarin test) and UV spectrum [(MeOH) λ_{max} 214, 238, 284, 325 nm]² together with the appearance of two 1H doublets [δ 7.98, *J* 9 Hz, H-4 and δ 6.50, *J* 9 Hz, H-3] in the 100 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum confirmed the presence of a coumarin system. The IR spectrum also disclosed the presence of a conjugated 6-membered δ-lactone (1700 and 1585 cm⁻¹). The functional group analysis revealed the presence of a methoxyl group (δ 3.88, 3H, s), an aliphatic ketone group (1878 cm⁻¹) and an epoxide (885 cm⁻¹)³. Moreover, the electronic absorption maxima were characteristic for 7-oxygenated coumarins^{2,4}. The ¹H NMR spectrum also confirmed the presence of unsubstituted C-6 (δ 6.46, 1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6) and C-8 (δ 6.54, 1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-8) of the 7-methoxycoumarin^{4,5}. The absence of H-5 signal in ¹H NMR spectrum confirmed the presence of a side chain at C-5. That the C-5 substituent is a 1-keto-2,3-dimethylpropan-2,3-epoxide, was evident from the IR spectrum (1878 cm⁻¹ for ketone and 885 cm⁻¹ for epoxide) and the ¹H NMR spectrum showed signals for a methine proton (δ 4.18, 1H,

q) and two methyl groups (δ 1.52, 3H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, and 1.44, 3H, s).

The mass spectrum showed an important peak of *m/z* 222 [M-52]⁺ corresponding to the loss of [CO + 2C] fragment from the M⁺ peak. The presence of a methoxyl group was confirmed by the expulsion of 15 a.m.u. from the peak at *m/z* 123 giving rise to a peak at *m/z* 108 which after expulsion of a hydrogen yielded the base peak at *m/z* 107.

Experimental

The plant material used in this investigation was obtained from the United Chemicals and Allied Products, 10 Clive Row, Kolkata, India where a voucher specimen is preserved.

Defatted and dried whole plant (3.5 kg) of *Gerbera lanuginosa* was extracted with benzene and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over silica gel. C₆H₆ eluted a dark brown gummy mass, which on rechromatography over silica gel yielded gerlanugin (yield 0.024%).

Gerlanugin (1) was obtained as colourless needles (hexane-chloroform) : m.p. 76–78°C (uncorr.); UV (MeOH) λ_{max} (log ε) 214 (4.4), 238 (4.2), 284 (4.2), 325 (4.2) nm; IR (nujol) ν_{max} 1878, 1700, 1585, 885, 800 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-4), 6.54 (1H, d,

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Note

J 2 Hz, H-8), 6.50 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-3), 6.46 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-6), 4.18 (1H, q, H-3'), 3.88 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 1.52 (3H, d, J 5.5 Hz, $-CH_3$), 1.44 (3H, s, $-CH_3$); EIMS m/z 274 $[M]^+$ (1.2), 222 (36.8), 207 (2.6), 202 (3.9), 178 (4.0), 159 (4.9), 152 (6.9), 151 (38.6), 131 (17.3), 130 (29.2), 124 (1.2), 123 (9.1), 108 (20.2), 107 (100), 103 (12.9), 102 (8.3), 79 (21.0), 71 (6.2), 51 (41.4), 44 (71.3); HREIMS m/z 274.0000 (calcd. for $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$, 274.000).

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